

THE PATRON

Gu ru 'phrin las ཀུ་རུ་འཕྲིན་ལས།*

It was an overcast, windy winter morning in Yellow River Township Town. As you might guess, it was on the icy banks of the Yellow River. The water was clear enough to see stones at the bottom of the river. A dirt road divided the town in half, with a few shops and restaurants on each side. Only one restaurant was open. The proprietress craned her neck from the restaurant door, scanning up and down the road. She was physically strong, and locals imagined she was also emotionally strong. Some called her "Strong Woman," partly because her tall stature, broad shoulders, long face, big eyes, and prominent straight nose made her look like a man when they saw her from a distance.

The street was empty of people and cars. Only a few dogs wandered around. A large, black dog padded to a garbage bin. A red mother dog that limped, not using her right hind leg, led two puppies. They sniffed a bone near the restaurant before lying in a circle around the bone. One puppy gnawed on the bone while the other two dogs seemed to doze.

When the black dog got near, the mother dog bared her fangs and furiously barked. The black dog gazed at the bone with an open mouth revealing sharp teeth, but it did not bark. Two strings of saliva ran down the sides of its mouth and hung from its chin. Suddenly, a whirlwind materialized, swirling the plastic bags, pieces of paper, and saliva strings into the sky.

The woman in her fifties moved back into her restaurant, and sitting at a table next to a stove, began stuffing dumplings with beef mince. She made twenty dumplings every other day. The restaurant owner only offered dumplings that cost one RMB each and complimentary tea to customers. After her husband had passed away from tuberculosis nine years after their marriage, increasingly fewer customers came to the restaurant. Sometimes, there were no customers for the whole day.

Her friends advised her to quit the business, but she refused. She wanted to serve a regular customer who chatted and even spent the whole day in the restaurant. Recently, he had not come. Feeling she had not seen him for months, she paused while stuffing the dumplings, counted on her fingers, put a piece of beef stuck on her right index finger into her mouth, swallowed, and murmured, "Thirty-six days."

She walked outside and looked around. The only living creatures she saw were the dogs. A robust, dust-laden gust of wind struck her and blew her red scarf off her shoulders. She trotted to where it fluttered on the dusty ground, but when she bent over to pick it up, the scarf bounded into the air. After finally grabbing it, she rushed back to her restaurant. With the scarf's cleaner end, she wiped the dust which had settled in her eyes. Standing near a window, she looked outside where a man threw stones at the black dog to make the dogs move away from a building with a white cross hospital symbol painted on the door.

The black dog seized the opportunity to grab the bone in its mouth and started to run away. The mother dog fiercely barked and tried to bite the black dog's tail and snatch the bone, but without success. The mother dog and her puppies ran after the black dog.

About a half-hour later, the man entered the restaurant carrying a plastic bag containing several medicine boxes. The restaurant was in a building that had a guest room, kitchen, and bedrooms. The kitchen and bedrooms were in one part of the house. Two tables were positioned on each side of the main door. Another table was next to the stove in the middle of the guest room. The man sat at the table near the stove and placed the bag on the table. The restaurant owner poured hot tea into a paper cup from a kettle on the stove and offered it to the man with her right hand. The man took the cup and removed his motorcycle helmet. She looked at the man's deep-set eyes and plump

*Gu ru 'phrin las. 2021. The Patron. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 60:402-405.

face. Realizing it was her deceased husband's brother, she smiled and said, "Oh... I didn't recognize you until you took off your helmet."

The man looked at her, smiled, sipped the tea, and said nothing.

"What brought you to town?" she asked.

"I came to get medicine for my son. He needs more."

"Your son was well a few days ago when I visited your family."

"When people get tuberculosis, they have to follow the doctor's orders and take medicine until they are completely recovered. It takes about a year."

They chatted about this and that until she got up, went to the kitchen, and returned with a plate of steaming dumplings. The pleasant smell of dumplings filled the room. She put the plate on the table and sat opposite the man. They ate the dumplings and enjoyed more conversation.

The man left when it got dark.

The woman was an outsider who had come to the town when she was forty-seven and opened the restaurant. She never talked about her parents to locals, who guessed she was an orphan. Three years later, she married a man two years older. After five years of marriage, her husband was diagnosed with spinal tuberculosis and soon couldn't move his legs. He spent his time in bed. After four years of suffering, death finally followed. Some locals criticized his wife for not giving him better care and not giving him medicine on time. Instead, they said, she was focused on her business.

Her brother-in-law thought differently. He said his brother's illness and death were fate.

After her husband's death, she visited her brother-in-law's home, where she would spend several nights at a time to lessen her loneliness. The last time she had visited, she had not spent the night because her brother-in-law was away.

Darkness came. Dogs occasionally barked in the distance. A few cars and motorcycles passed noisily in the street. The restaurant owner came outside, tossed garbage near the bin, and glanced around before peeing near the garbage bin. She then went inside and closed the restaurant's door.

In bed that night, she tossed and turned, unable to sleep. She prayed that the man she hadn't seen for thirty-six days would be standing at the door of her restaurant when she opened it the following day.

At midnight, a man in his sixties was awakened by his wife's laugh. She slept in an adjoining room. Half-awake and half-asleep, the man yawned, lifted his head, and listened to his wife talking on the phone. He put his blanket over his head, lay back down, and attempted to sleep, but his wife's noise bothered him. He walked to his bedroom door, but he hesitated as he was about to open the door. He was sure his wife had locked her bedroom door and would not open it if he knocked.

He returned to his bed, faced the adjoining wall, and tried to shout, but nothing came from his mouth. He knew it was better to leave her alone. When he had shouted before, he'd got no response, which made him angry. He covered his head with a blanket and murmured, "What a crazy old woman!"

The next day, the man got up around noon, walked into the kitchen, looked around, and noticed a half-full pot of thin noodles with bits of beef. He took a bowl and a pair of chopsticks from a shelf and poured the stuck-together noodles into the bowl. He sat at a table in the living room. His wife's bowl was on the table, with a single noodle stuck to the side of the bowl remaining inside. He again heard his wife on the phone in her bedroom. He ate half of the noodles in his bowl, left the bowl on the table, went into his bedroom, looked into a mirror on the wall, and combed his short black hair. He shrugged into his leather jacket and left home.

Two young men were having lunch in the dumpling restaurant. One looked at the proprietress and whispered, "What an unhappy woman! I've never seen her smile."

The other young man popped a steaming dumpling into his mouth, glanced at her gloomy face, and nodded in agreement.

The woman added water more into the kettle on the stove and didn't hear, or pretended not to hear, what the young man had said.

The man in the leather jacket peeked into the restaurant and stepped back when he saw the two young men but suddenly changed his mind and entered. He sat silently at a table near the door.

As soon as the woman noticed, she smiled and offered the man tea. The man realized the two young men were whispering and snickering when she sat at his table. He wanted to say something to the young men but instead sipped the tea and said nothing.

The woman ignored the young men, happily chatting with the man. The man frequently glanced at the two young men sitting at the table in the other corner near the door.

One of the young men gave the woman thirty RMB, which she put in her apron pocket. She took a glass cup from the table near the stove and poured tea for herself. She then sat again with the man saying, "Don't pay attention to those guys."

"I don't know why locals think I betrayed my wife and am having an affair with you."

"Don't care what others say. They like to spread rumors about everyone, not only us."

"There's nothing wrong with me coming here and talking with you. We enjoy chatting with one another."

"That's right," the woman declared, poured more tea into the man's cup, and asked, "Where have you been? I haven't seen you for days."

"I stayed at home and spent time with my daughter who was on winter holiday. She returned to school yesterday."

"Where does she study?"

"I forgot the name of her university. It's in the capital city."

"You're lucky. You have a daughter and wife. I have no children, and my husband is gone. When a person lives alone..." She stopped and put her head down, not finishing what she had intended to say.

The man paused and said, "Yeah. But sometimes, I want to divorce. My wife's siblings suggested we shouldn't divorce on the grounds they would be shamed if their sister in her fifties was divorced. They also think it would destroy my wife and my daughter's reputations."

The woman looked at his dark, gaunt face and didn't say anything.

"I haven't talked to my wife for a year. We only eat together when our daughter is at home. Every child wants their parents to live together. My daughter will be happy if we stay together. She tells her mother and me about one of her girlfriends who was extroverted and talkative, but became aloof and disengaged socially isolated after her parents divorced."

The proprietress thought he definitely should divorce if he suffered being with his wife. She could spend more time with him once he was divorced. But she also realized it would be hard for him once he divorced with no relatives and few friends in town. Locals had generally been kind to her and had come to her restaurant when her husband was alive. After he died, things changed. There were very few customers, and only her brother-in-law was kind to her. She recalled her childhood. Her parents had divorced when she was six, and then her maternal grandmother had cared for her. Her grandmother's favorite food was beef dumplings. The little girl helped make dumplings, and her grandmother rewarded her by allowing her to play with her friends afterward. She felt she was different and unlucky and admired her friends who had parents that stayed together.

At that time, one of her playmates, a mischievous boy, had long, messy hair that hung over his shoulders. He often breathed through his nose when snot ran into his mouth. At times, he wiped his nose with the back of his right hand and rubbed it on his tattered pants' legs.

He asked the little girl, "Where did your father go?"

"My father went to town," she answered, her face turning red.

"Your father hasn't returned home for days. My father goes to town and buys me candy. It only takes a day. What's wrong with your father?"

The little girl put her head down and played with a white and black stone in her hands. The stones were smooth, round, and small. She held one in each hand.

The next time the boy asked her the same question, she said impatiently, "I told you my father went to town!"

The boy pushed the little girl so hard that she fell and said, "Liar!" and ran to his home.

The little girl jumped up and threw the black stone at the boy. It missed. Tears ran down her cheeks. A playmate wiped her tears away with her hand and consoled her. The little girl stopped crying, held the white stone in her right hand, and slowly walked home.

Not knowing what to say, the proprietress offered no suggestions.

They talked till dusk when the man got ready to leave. She urged him to chat more. Although he wanted to, he knew locals would gossip the next day if they talked too late into the night. "You know people circulate rumors about others," he said, looking slowly around the restaurant for a few seconds and then walked toward the door.

She said, "You're the only person I feel close to. We understand each other. Time goes by so quickly when I'm with you."

The man looked at her, smiled, gripped. Turning the doorknob, he stepped outside. Following him, she stood by the door and said, "I'll open the restaurant early tomorrow morning. I always welcome you. You are my only regular customer."

The man smiled broadly, nodded, said goodbye, and strode in the direction of his home.

When she could no longer see him, she went inside.

The proprietress usually was unable to fall asleep until midnight, but this night was different.

Two hours later, as it began snowing, dogs howled in the distance. The wind blew against the windows, making them tremble, but none of this disturbed her. She was deeply asleep and smiling, snuggled under a blanket.

The next day was sunny.

The black dog and the mother dog were peacefully leading the puppies along the street in the evening, amicably walking together. The proprietress stopped looking at the dogs and gazed in the direction of her only regular customer's home.